

A Life to Live Beyond Orthopaedics

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Why we have chosen Orthopaedics for ourselves? There can many personalized reasons for the above, but the commoner are – its lucrative, paying, satisfying, early practice settlement, definitive and terminal branch. There are hardly any females in the branch; hence Orthopaedic branch is totally all boys party without any inhibitions. They have all sorts of fun and enjoyment. Orthopods live life king size.

The various modes of leisure for orthopods are parties, exercises/physical activity/gyming followed by travelling, food and wine, whereas less common in them are music and arts (photography, painting, sculpture). Party with friends, colleagues or family members is most common form of enjoyment for orthopods and most of orthopaedicians are party animals having regular parties. On an average orthopods do party or attend functions about one per week. These parties are full with boozing and smoking and almost more than 80 % of the surgeons are drinkers in these parties having average more than two drinks per day. Only 20% of orthopaedic surgeons are non-drinkers. About 30 % of the orthopaedicians are smokers, among which 20 % are chain smokers. Many of the academic conferences, short table gatherings and group discussions held over the dinner table for orthopaedic surgeons arranged by the pharmaceuticals are for alcohol only. Many of the academic meetings attended by the members outside the hometown are not for academic content, but only for the food, alcohol, banquet or entertainment, outside the hometown as they are away from inhibitions. These gatherings between the orthopod surgeons is always with adult jokes and abusive slangs which is commonly done over smoke and booze. The average happiness rating for an orthopaedician is 3.96 out of 5.

Orthopaedic surgery, as a branch is rewarding profession, but it is a very demanding also. Orthopaedics is a hectic, intense and stressful

branch. It needs high learning curve in lesser time and lot of physical effort. Being an emergency branch, emergency duties can be day and night and you need to attend, manage and sometimes may have to operate also in odd hours, which when started, there is no warranty when will it end. The load, burden, malpractice and negligence allegations are increasing day by day, thus it is increasing the practice risk and now there is very less margin of error. This time commitment can negatively impact family time and adversely affect work life balance. It is common for Orthopods in the bedroom, having sleepless night thinking that how could that screw go out during the surgery. We can commonly see orthopaedicians using derogative language and abusive words in operation theatres and hospitals among themselves and to patients even. Being all boys party, there is lack of softness and politeness of the behaviour of many of the orthopaedicians as well. Further the cut throat competition and decline in ethical values have led to envy among themselves and with others. These have made the life of an orthopaedician difficult and stressful and also have affected their family-life, with equal increase in rate of remarriage and divorce.

This stressful and demanding life among us has lead us to seek measures to overcome stress. We seek pleasures in dealing with this intense and hectic life of orthopaedic surgeon. We seek this escapism in smoking and boozing, which at times and for few of us is over the acceptable limit. The competition between the minded maniacs for smoking and drinking crosses the barriers and it has made many of our friends addicted even. This along with stressful life, sedentary habits and medical comorbidities like hypertension and diabetes has made us vulnerable for serious problems. In recent time, we have lost eminent orthopods for the unknown reasons, the damages of which cannot be repent. Many

of our orthopaedic surgeons are still dealing with some serious chronic morbidities and terminal illnesses, most of which could be prevented.

As it is rightly said Orthopedic surgeons are "strong as an ox and twice as smart", but we as an orthopaedic surgeon should strive for a balanced life to care for ourselves and our families as well as profession. We want work satisfaction and healing touch for our patients. At the same time we owe responsibility to family. Its a bitter truth that only family will be with us in all our difficult times. Neglecting family life for excelling professionally does happen in lives of many of us. No one will remember you for working day in and day night or working on weekends when others are enjoying. Its imperative to strike a critical balance between work and family life. Mobile phone is again a big stress for a doctor. Patients in India feel it their right to call on a doctors mobile at any time for petty issues. Many of us don't switch off mobiles even on vacations for the fear of loosing patients. Another area is Professional jousting. At times we get complications from other colleague and patients and their relatives try to make us talk about the previous orthopods alleged mistakes. Many times we receive x rays on Whats app seeking opinions from patients. We need to be very careful on such situations as today litigations against doctors are on a rise. If we talk something loose about any

colleague, some or the other day it is bound to backfire on us.

What needs to be done, is balance between the professional and personal life. In professional life we needs to focus on limitations of our body as well as mind. Rather than treating ourselves as machine consider ourselves human. Professionally, strict to the duties towards patient by being understanding, honest, polite, competent, ethical and committed and have empathy towards patients. Towards our peer members we need to be respectful and should not be involved in medical jousting and entice. We should keep our self-updated and should not be overburdened and exhaustive. Admit Our limitations and overcome the shortenings. In personal life we need to take time for leisure, family and friend and not the least for ourselves. Keep yourself simple and low maintained. Keep time for your hobby like traveling, shopping, singing, painting, playing or music etc. Nurture your relations with family and friends. Take care of your health with balanced diet and light exercises.

Finally we want to be happy and healthy, caring and competent and good travel companions for people through the journey we call life, which can be done by none other than we ourselves.

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